

Mendeley Reference Manager and Zotero Instalation

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Mengenal tools Management Reference Mendeley Reference Manager dan Zotero

1. Sebuah tools yang membantu menuliskan daftar rujukan dan daftar pustaka pada sebuah artikel.
2. Mendeley dan zotero sama-sama sebuah tools yang membantu author membantu menuliskan daftar rujukan dan daftar pustaka secara gratis.

Mengapa menggunakan tools management reference?

1. Lebih mudah
2. Konsisten
3. Menghindari referensi yang tidak tertulis pada artikel kita
4. Dapat digunakan untuk pencarian artikel, penyimpanan artikel dan PDF Viewer

Mendeley

1. Mendeley memiliki 2 jenis alat yaitu mendeley desktop dan mendeley reference manager
2. Mendeley desktop akan dihapus September 2022 dan permanen menjadi Mendeley Reference Manager
3. Cara menggunakan sama yaitu pada tahap awal author dapat register pada alat tersebut.
4. Mendeley yang akan saya peragakan adalah Mendeley Reference Manager dengan ms word online
5. Mengapa ms word online? Karena MRM menggunakan sign in akun ms word sehingga ms word kita wajib original

MRM dengan ms word online

1. Register pada ms word online
2. Buka ms word online
3. Klik insert dan pilih mendeley cite
4. Login MRM
5. MRM dapat digunakan

MRM dengan ms word online

1. Create new acun (isikan semua isian saat kita registrasi pada ms word online)

MRM dengan ms word online

Klik insert klik add in mendeley cite

MRM dengan ms word online

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Word online interface with the 'Add-in Office' search results for 'mendeley ci'. The search results are sorted by popularity and include the following add-ins:

Add-in Name	Description	Rating	Action
Mendeley Cite	Cite as you write. Generate citations and bibliographies and change your citation style.	★★★★☆ (1140)	Tambahkan
SmartCite for Papers	Cite references and generate bibliographies automatically from your ReadCube Papers library!	★★★★☆ (154)	Tambahkan
Petal Cite Word Add-in	Cite references and generate bibliographies		Tambahkan

The interface also shows the 'Sisipkan' (Insert) tab selected in the ribbon, and the 'Add-in Office' search bar containing 'mendeley ci'. The search results are displayed in a list with a search bar and a 'Urutkan berdasarkan: Popularitas' dropdown menu.

Mendeley

MRM dengan ms word online

The screenshot displays the Microsoft Word online interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: <https://onedrive.live.com/edit.aspx?action=editnew&resid=4908A6BF3A58605B1111&ihint=file%2cdocx&action=edi...>. The Word ribbon is visible with the 'Referensi' (References) tab selected. The 'Mendeley Cite' sidebar is open on the right, featuring the Mendeley logo and the text 'Mendeley Cite' and 'Cite as you write'. The sidebar lists three features: 'Access references from your Mendeley Library', 'Insert auto-formatted citations and bibliography', and 'Choose the right citation style for your article'. A 'Get started' button is present at the bottom of the sidebar. The main document area is currently blank. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system tray with the date and time: 17:19, 12/06/2022.

MRM dengan ms word online

MRM dengan ms word online

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Word online interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Word', 'Dokumen - Disimpan ke OneDrive', and a search bar. The ribbon menu is set to 'Referensi' (References). The 'Mendeley Cite' sidebar is open on the right, displaying a list of references:

- Islamic Finance and Law Theory and Practice in a Globalized World**
Balala M
London, I.B. Tauris Co.Ltd, (2011), 23
- Al-fiqh ala Madzahabil Arba'ah**
Al-Jaziri A
Mesir, Dar al-Fikr, (1989), 278
- Rise of A national Contract Law in the Age of Globalization, The**

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system tray with the date 12/06/2022 and time 17:26.

Zotero

1. Register zotero dan download zotero
2. Login zotero
3. Buka zotero desktop
4. Insatal zotero ms word

Zotero

1. Register zotero dan download zotero

zotero

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Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Zotero

1. Login zotero
2. Buka akun zotero desktop

Zotero

1. Register zotero dan download zotero
2. Login zotero
3. Buka zotero desktop

Zotero

1. Register zotero dan download zotero
2. Login zotero
3. Buka zotero desktop
4. Insatal zotero ms word

Mendeley

Z Add-ons Manager × Upgrade Storage

File Edit

Extensions

Zotero LibreOffice Integration
Integrates Zotero with LibreOffice and OpenOffice.org 3.0 or l... [More](#) Dis

Zotero Word for Windows Integration
Integrates Zotero with Microsoft Word for Windows [More](#) Dis

- Check for Updates
- View Recent Updates
- Install Add-on From File...
- Debug Add-ons
- Update Add-ons Automatically
- Reset All Add-ons to Update Automatically

in this view

MENDELEY
ADVISOR ID

Mendeley

감사합니다 Natick
 Danke Ευχαριστίες Dalu
 Grazie Thank You Köszönöm
 Спасибо Dank Gracias
 谢谢 Merci Seé
 ありがとう
 Obrigado

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JURNAL INDONESIA